

USED DISPOSABLE NAPPIES AND EXPIRED FOOD PRODUCTS VALORIZATION THROUGH ONE- & TWO-STAGE ANAEROBIC CO- DIGESTION

Konstantina Tsigkou^a, Panagiota Tsafrakidou^b, Alexandros Kopsahelis^a, Dimitris Zagklis^b,
Constantina Zafiri^b, Michael Kornaros^{a,*}

^a *Laboratory of Biochemical Engineering and Environmental Technology (LBEET), Department of
Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, University Campus, Patras, GR-26504, Greece*

^b *Green Technologies Ltd, 5 Ellinos Stratiotou Str., Patras, GR-26223, Greece*

*Corresponding author. Tel.: +30 2610 997418; Fax: +30 2610 969584

E-mail address: kornaros@chemeng.upatras.gr (M. Kornaros)

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Highlights

- One- & two-stage anaerobic co-digestion of Disposable Nappies & EFP were compared
- The highest H₂ production yield was observed in acidogenesis at HRT 2 d and pH 6.0
- The highest CH₄ yield was observed in two-stage operation at HRT 25 d
- Two-stage operation had 18.4% higher energy production than one-stage
- COD removal reached 80% in the two-stage AD system

1 **USED DISPOSABLE NAPPIES AND EXPIRED FOOD**
2 **PRODUCTS VALORIZATION THROUGH ONE- & TWO-STAGE**
3 **ANAEROBIC CO-DIGESTION**

4 Konstantina Tsigkou^a, Panagiota Tsafrakidou^b, Alexandros Kopsahelis^a, Dimitris
5 Zagklis^b, Constantina Zafiri^b, Michael Kornaros^{a,*}

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7 ^a*Laboratory of Biochemical Engineering and Environmental Technology (LBEET),*
8 *Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, University Campus, Patras,*
9 *GR-26504, Greece*

10 ^b*Green Technologies Ltd, 5 Ellinos Stratiotou Str., Patras, GR-26223, Greece*

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15 *Corresponding author. Tel.: +30 2610 997418; Fax: +30 2610 969584

16 *E-mail address:* kornaros@chemeng.upatras.gr (M. Kornaros)

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23 Declarations of interest: none

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25 **ABSTRACT**

26

27 In the present work, an innovative approach of used disposable nappies (DN)
28 treatment is presented aiming at energy recovery through anaerobic co-digestion of
29 their biodegradable content along with a waste fraction containing expired food
30 products (EFP). More specifically, a mixture of hydrolysate, prepared from used
31 disposable nappies with pulverized fruits/vegetables that have lost their retail value,
32 was used as feedstock in two- and one-stage mesophilic anaerobic digestion systems
33 at a 60:40 (v/v) ratio. For the two-stage experiments, different combinations of pH
34 and Hydraulic Retention Time (HRT) were tested in the acidogenic and
35 methanogenic reactor. The performance of the system, operated at steady-state
36 conditions, in terms of COD removal, digestion stability, and biofuels (H₂ and CH₄)
37 production, was compared with that obtained from the one-stage configuration. The
38 comparison between the two systems revealed that COD removal reached 80% in the
39 two-stage system, but only 68% in the one-stage. At HRT 25d the yield of produced
40 methane in the methanogenic reactor of the two-stage system reached the theoretical
41 value of 0.35 L_{CH₄}/g_{t-COD} removed. Comparing the two-stage system, operated at
42 HRT 15d, with the one-stage system, it was evident that the energy production of the
43 two-stage system was higher by 18.4%.

44

45 *Keywords:* disposable nappies, expired food products, anaerobic co-digestion, two-
46 stage system, biogas, biohydrogen

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48

49 **1. Introduction**

50

51 Used disposable nappies represent 2% to 15% of the municipal solid waste
52 (MSW) globally (Arena et al., 2016; Espinosa-Valdemar et al., 2014). Among the
53 components comprising a disposable nappy are fluffy pulp (cellulose fibres), which is
54 part of the absorbent core layer, and the excreta (urine and faeces) it contains, thus
55 making organic materials a notable percentage in this type of waste reaching almost
56 90% (Colon et al., 2010). Despite the significant proportion of recyclable materials in
57 this waste stream, it is currently disposed of to landfills or led to incineration, due to
58 its collection with unsorted Municipal Solid Wastes (MSW) (Colon et al., 2013;
59 Arena et al., 2016). Used disposable nappies are characterized by a residency time in
60 landfills up to 500 years. Therefore, it is essential to investigate various sustainable
61 management solutions for the effective treatment of these wastes and promote
62 separate collection towards their valorization.

63 In addition, EU food waste from wholesale and retail account for almost 5
64 million tonnes per year (Stenmarck et al., 2016). This sector of the supply chain in
65 Greece and other EU countries follows a returning policy of the expired food products
66 (EFP) or the faulty products that do not preserve their retail value to the production
67 companies. Only fruit and vegetables are treated with conventional waste
68 management methods such as landfilling, leaving their valuable components like
69 carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals unexploited (Han et al., 2015; Nathia-Neves et
70 al., 2018).

71 The solution of landfilling should no longer play the pivotal role of waste
72 management, due to both environmental and public health safety risks but also
73 because of waste framework directives. EU Landfill Directive (99/31/EC) of 31st

74 April, necessitates the reduction of biodegradable waste disposal in landfills, while
75 European Directive 2008/98/EC (08/98/EC) suggests that the following waste
76 hierarchy should be applied: prevention, preparation for re-use, recycling, other
77 recovery (such as energy recovery) and disposal. Energy recovery can be achieved
78 through anaerobic digestion (AD), which is widely used for the treatment of MSW
79 equally with composting (Paramaguru et al., 2017). Besides energy generation, AD
80 presents other benefits as well, like greenhouse gas mitigation and a stabilized
81 digestate that could be also valorized through composting for soil enhancement
82 (Dogan and Demirer, 2012; Behera et al., 2010). The efficiency of the process
83 depends on various parameters that have been reported in literature, like one- or two-
84 stage systems (Nathao et al., 2013; Micolucci et al., 2018), pH (Dareioti et al., 2014;
85 Paramaguru et al., 2017), HRT (Dareioti and Kornaros, 2014, 2015), pretreatment
86 (Naran et al., 2016), substrate shift (Carvalheira et al., 2018), microbial community
87 and characteristics (Zhao et al., 2018) and co-digestion which is a well-established
88 technology with consistent results in boosting the production of gaseous biofuels
89 (Edwards et al., 2017). One of the advantages of the simultaneous digestion of two or
90 more substrates is that it dilutes toxic compounds that usually inhibit the operation of
91 the bioreactors (Angeriz-Campoy et al., 2015), but also facilitates the anaerobic
92 digestion process by balancing nutrients and reducing the cost of managing each
93 stream separately via equipment sharing.

94 Besides the use of two or more substrates as feedstock, one- or two-stage
95 configuration of the anaerobic system is crucial for the final energy production and
96 stability of the process (Schievano et al., 2014). The separation of the H₂ production
97 phase from methanogenesis has been investigated by many scientists. Regarding food
98 waste, Xiao et al. (2018) reported recently a comparison between one- and two-stage

99 anaerobic digestion under thermophilic conditions, where they compared energy
100 yields, methane content of the produced biogas, methane yields, and reaction rates
101 between the two configurations. Another late attempt compared the energy recovery
102 between the two configurations for the anaerobic digestion of food waste (De
103 Gioannis et al., 2017), while Voelklein et al. (2016) studied the impact of loading rate
104 increase on the two-stage anaerobic digestion compared to a single-stage system.

105 The objective of this study was to investigate the co-digestion of used
106 disposable nappies (DN) and expired food products (EFP) through one- and two-stage
107 anaerobic continuous systems, by exploiting their energy content in the most efficient
108 and productive way in terms of energy, i.e. hydrogen and methane production. **The**
109 **obligatory pre-treatment step of DN, for the removal of plastics and other non-bio-**
110 **degradable polymers for the preparation of the hydrolysate that contains the**
111 **biodegradable material, results to a waste stream with a low COD value that comes**
112 **mostly from cellulose fibres and excreta. Regarding lignocellulosic materials like DN,**
113 **the rate limiting step of anaerobic digestion is hydrolysis, which is hindered by the**
114 **their complex and compact structure and the presence of lignin that inhibits enzymatic**
115 **activity (Yu et al., 2004; Ma et al., 2013). In order to surpass this adversity, EFP that**
116 **contain high amounts of soluble organic material and COD content, were introduced**
117 **in the feedstock of the digesters. Co-digestion was proposed as a management**
118 **solution, for the simultaneous valorisation of a not easily degradable waste stream**
119 **(DN) and the waste stream (food waste) that represents the highest percentage among**
120 **the Municipal Solid Wastes (Abad et al., 2019). Gaseous biofuels production was**
121 **monitored in order to draw comparative conclusions on the efficiency of each**
122 **configuration.** More specifically, in the two-stage system, different combinations of
123 pH and HRT were tested, while both reactors were also operated as one-stage systems

124 for comparison reasons.

125

126 **2. Materials and Methods**

127

128 *2.1 Anaerobic digestion feedstock and inoculum*

129

130 A hydrolysate from used disposable nappies (DN), prepared according to
131 Conway et al. (1996), was used as feedstock for co-digestion with pulped fruit and
132 vegetables that have lost their retail value. Used disposable nappies were obtained
133 from a Greek private nursery in Patras (Achaia, Greece), while the expired food
134 products (EFP) containing only fruits and vegetables, originated from a Greek
135 Supermarket chain. The ratio of the feedstock was 60% DN and 40% (v/v) EFP. Both
136 EFP and DN were stored separately at -18 °C until further use.

137 Anaerobic sludge, obtained from a wastewater treatment plant in
138 Metamorphosis (Attiki, Greece), was used as inoculum at 15% v/v in the acidogenic
139 reactor. The sludge was boiled at 100 °C for 20 min, prior to experiments, in order to
140 enrich hydrogen-producing bacteria via the deactivation of methanogens and H₂
141 consumers (Wang and Wan, 2008). The methanogenic reactor was filled (100%) with
142 the untreated sludge for the start-up of the system. The total solids (TS) content of the
143 sludge was 54.85 g/L, while the VS/TS ratio was 42%.

144

145 *2.2 Experimental set-up and procedure*

146

147 The co-digestion was carried out in mesophilic (37±0.5 °C) conditions,
148 controlled via a thermocouple and maintained constant by hot water circulation, in two

149 continuous stirred tank reactors (CSTR). The working volumes were 750 mL and 4L,
 150 for the acidogenic and the methanogenic reactor respectively. Both reactors were
 151 cylindrical, double-walled and made of stainless steel (INOX316). On top of each
 152 reactor, a geared motor drive unit was installed to ensure continuous agitation.

153 pH of the acidogenic reactor was automatically controlled (HACH controller,
 154 SC200) and kept constant with the addition of 1N NaOH-KOH solution through a
 155 peristaltic pump. Two pH values were tested (5.5 and 6.0) based on preliminary tests.
 156 The feedstock was stored in a tank, placed in a refrigerator to maintain its temperature
 157 at 4 °C and was fed to the acidogenic reactor via a precise peristaltic pump, every 1.5 h
 158 (16 times per day) for 7 sec. The effluent from this reactor was used as feedstock for
 159 the methanogenic one and was fed through a second peristaltic pump at the same
 160 frequency.

161 The system operated also as one-stage acidogenic and one-stage methanogenic.
 162 In the first case, the peristaltic pump that sent the effluent from the acidogenic reactor
 163 to the methanogenic one was deactivated, whereas in the second case, the acidogenic
 164 reactor was bypassed and the feedstock from the feeding tank was sent directly to the
 165 methanogenic reactor. The operating conditions of all tested Runs of the system are
 166 presented in **Table1**.

167

168 **Table 1.** Operating conditions of the compared anaerobic systems

Run	I	Ila	Ilb	Ilc	III	IV
One- stage	-	-	-	-	+	+
Two-stage	+	+	+	+	-	-
pH Ac.	5.5	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.5	-
HRT Ac. (d)	2	2	2	2	1.5	-

HRT Meth. (d)	25	25	15	10	-	15
Operation (d)	68	16	31	6	10	41
OLR Meth.	0.92 kg _{VS} /m ³ d (1.75 kg _{COD} /m ³ d)	0.92 kg _{VS} /m ³ d (1.75 kg _{COD} /m ³ d)	1.54 kg _{VS} /m ³ d (3.36 kg _{COD} /m ³ d)	2.3 kg _{VS} /m ³ d (4.60 kg _{COD} /m ³ d)	-	1.54 kg _{VS} /m ³ d (3.36 kg _{COD} /m ³ d)

169

170 Biogas volume was measured automatically by a custom-made device,
 171 operating via a combination of a U-tube filled with engine oil, an electron – valve and
 172 a counter. The measurement was based on counting the number of displacements of
 173 constant oil volume by the produced biogas. **Fig. 1** illustrates the experimental
 174 apparatus.

175

176 **Figure 1.** Experimental apparatus of the anaerobic co-digestion system.

177

178 2.3 Analytical methods

179

180 The characterization of each feedstock and their mixture, as well as the
 181 effluent of the reactor, included determination of the following parameters: pH,

182 alkalinity, total and soluble chemical oxygen demand (t-COD, s-COD), total and
183 soluble carbohydrates (**t-Carbohydrates**, **s-Carbohydrates**), soluble phenolic
184 compounds, total and soluble phosphorus, total (TS) and volatile (VS) solids,
185 total (TSS) and volatile (VSS) suspended solids, total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN),
186 ammonium nitrogen (NH₃-N) and fats/oils. All analyses were performed in
187 triplicate. The off-line pH was measured using a pH meter with an electrode
188 (Thermo Scientific, Orion ROSS Ultra Refillable pH/ATC Triode). Alkalinity,
189 TS, VS, TSS, VSS, COD, TKN, ammonium nitrogen, total and dissolved
190 phosphorus were determined according to *Standard Methods* (APHA, 2012).
191 Carbohydrates were measured according to Joseffson (1983), phenolic
192 compounds were determined, as syringic acid equivalents, according to
193 Waterman and Mole (1994), and fats/oils were measured after extraction with
194 hexane using a Soxhlet extractor (Velp Scientifica, SER 148).

195 **Quantification of main elements C, O, H, N and S was performed on**
196 **freeze-dried (Telstar, LyoQuest) samples with an elemental analyser (EA3000,**
197 **Eurovector). Approximately 10 mg of each sample were weighed into tin**
198 **capsules. Samples were placed into the combustion chamber (~1000 °C) through**
199 **a sampling probe, then oxygen was introduced, and the temperature was raised**
200 **up to 1300-1400 °C, with tin acting as a catalyst. The solid samples were**
201 **oxidized to gases CO₂, H₂O, NO_x and SO₃ and then, after their reduction, a gas**
202 **mixture consisting of N₂, CO₂, H₂O and SO₂ was obtained. Finally, the gas**
203 **mixture was analysed through gas chromatography with a packed column**
204 **(Porapack Q) and a thermal conductivity detector (TCD).**

205 Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) and ethanol (EtOH) were analysed by a gas
206 chromatograph (Agilent Technologies, 7890A) equipped with a capillary column

207 (DB–FFAP, 30 m in length, 0.25 mm I.D. and 0.25 μ m film) and a flame
208 ionization detector. Helium was used as carrier gas.

209 Biogas samples were taken with a syringe from the top of the reactor.
210 The gas composition (H_2 , CH_4 , CO_2) was determined using a gas
211 chromatography using a capillary column (HP-PLOT/Q, 30 m in length, 0.53
212 mm I.D. and 40 μ m packing film), a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and
213 nitrogen as carrier gas.

214

215 **3. Results and Discussion**

216

217 *3.1 Feedstock physicochemical characterization*

218

219 The feedstock was monitored regarding its physicochemical
220 characteristics throughout the experimentation period in order to ensure that its
221 composition remained constant. As shown in **Table 2**, EFP present high organic
222 content and carbohydrates. More specifically, 77.7% of the carbohydrates are
223 soluble, therefore this substrate does not require further hydrolytic pre-treatment
224 prior to the anaerobic digestion process. Its pH is acidic (4.34 ± 0.22) and the
225 VS/TS ratio is 92.9%. TKN reaches 1.29 g/L and NH_3-N 0.04 g/L, leading to the
226 conclusion that most of its nitrogen content is organic. EFP present a COD:N:P
227 ratio of 389:4:1, and a percentage of C and N of 50.6% and 2% in dry matter,
228 respectively.

229 DN hydrolysate presents lower values on almost all parameters, except
230 pH (7.77 ± 0.04) and humidity ($99.19\pm 0.10\%$). Neutral to alkaline pH value is due
231 to decomposition of urea and urate, which are present in the urine content of the

232 DN (Kirchmann and Pettersson, 1994). All nitrogen content originates from
233 ammonia (0.26 ± 0.02 g/L). Low concentrations of COD (5.87 ± 1.26 g/L),
234 carbohydrates (1.37 ± 0.13 g/L) and other characteristics are attributed to the high
235 dilution ratio due to the pre-treatment process. Cellulose and excreta of DN
236 represent the TS (8.07 ± 0.97 g/L) of this substrate. The COD:N:P ratio is
237 293.5:13:1, while the percentages of C and N reach 30.4% and 1.7% in dry
238 matter, respectively.

239 Finally, the mixture of DN and EFP (60% and 40%, v/v respectively)
240 which is used as feedstock for the process, has lower organic load than EFP with
241 t-COD 48.9 g/L. The VS/TS ratio is 86.9% and the COD:N:P is 264.6:2.3:1,
242 which is close to the optimum operational ratio for anaerobic processes (350:7:1)
243 (Nguyen et al., 2015). In addition, the C/N ratio (26.38) is also within the range
244 of the optimum values for anaerobic digestion (20-30) (Hallaji et al., 2019).

245

246 3.2 Acidogenic reactor.

247

248 The acidogenic reactor operated as two- and one-stage system. During
249 the two-stage operation, HRT remained constant at 2 d and two pH values were
250 tested, 5.5 and 6.0 (Run I and II), while there has been an attempt to reduce HRT
251 at 1.5 d with pH 5.5, at the one-stage treatment (Run III). A consequence of the
252 HRT reduction was the increment of the organic load rate (OLR) from 24.1 kg
253 COD/m³d to 33.9 kg COD/m³d (**Table 2**) and the reduction of the produced H₂.

254

255

256

257 **Table 2.** Physico-chemical composition of feedstock used in this study. Data are mean
 258 values (n=3, ± SD)

Parameter	DN (SD)	EFP (SD)	Mix 60%DN:40%EFP (SD)
pH	7.77 (0.04)	4.34 (0.22)	5.01 (0.3)
t-Carbohydrates (g _{glucose} /L)	1.37 (0.13)	109.20 (5.66)	35.22 (7.3)
s-Carbohydrates (g _{glucose} /L)	0.24 (0.01)	84.90 (4.76)	23.59 (2.75)
s-phenolic compounds (g _{syringic acid} /L)	0.04 (0.00)	0.6 (0.03)	0.22 (0.05)
t-COD (g/L)	5.87 (1.26)	124.55 (2.89)	48.9 (3.5)
s-COD (g/L)	1.51 (0.22)	62.75 (1.33)	30.2 (5.0)
t-Phosphorus (g/L)	0.02 (0.00)	0.32 (0.01)	0.19 (0.02)
d-Phosphorus (g/L)	0.02 (0.00)	0.23 (0.01)	0.12 (0.01)
TKN (g/L)	0.26 (0.02)	1.29 (0.09)	0.43 (0.02)
NH ₃ -N (g/L)	0.26 (0.02)	0.04 (0.00)	0.16 (0.03)
TSS (g/L)	4.45 (0.18)	32.50 (4.44)	13.61 (2.15)
VSS (g/L)	4.30 (0.32)	30.33 (3.01)	13.17 (2.00)
TS (g/L)	8.07 (0.97)	92.51 (1.96)	26.7 (1.9)
VS (g/L)	4.99 (0.98)	85.92 (1.17)	23.2 (2.01)
Humidity (%)	99.19 (0.10)	90.75 (0.20)	97.33 (0.40)
C (%) *	30.4	50.6	47.5
N (%) *	1.7	2	1.8
H (%) *	5	2.5	3.2
O (%) *	43.7	33.5	36.1
S (%) *	0.2	0.2	0.2
C/N	17.88	25.30	26.38

259 *% in dry matter

260 In addition, TSS and VSS presented in **Fig. 2**, remained at a range between 10
 261 to 15 g/L throughout the operation of acidogenesis. Therefore, in order to ensure that
 262 sufficient hydrolysis of the organic matter took place, the HRT was kept at 2 d even
 263 though in literature it has been reported that this stage can last hours (Dareioti et al.,
 264 2014; Lee et al., 2013). TSS of the acidogenic reactor effluent were 12.69 ± 1.83 g/L
 265 with 95.5% of them being VSS. De Gioannis et al. (2017), mention a VS removal of
 266 the same magnitude during acidogenesis of food waste with HRT 26 h and conclude
 267 that CO₂ production is responsible for the limited loss of organic carbon (De Gioannis
 268 et al. 2017). They report that most of the carbon content remains in the liquid phase of
 269 the acidogenesis effluent and can be further converted to methane during
 270 methanogenesis in the second reactor, as previously reported by other researchers
 271 (Alibardi and Cossu, 2016). On the contrary, Ganesh et al. (2014) report high
 272 solubilization of the fruit and vegetable waste they treated, during a two-stage
 273 operation at an OLR of 7.0 Kg_{VS}/m³d with a pH value of 5.5-6.2.

274

275

276 **Figure 2.** Evolution of total suspended solids (TSS) and volatile suspended solids
277 (VSS) concentration during acidogenesis for each HRT and pH tested.

278

279 The extent of hydrolysis taking place during acidogenesis was also monitored
280 by the evolution of COD (**Fig. 3**). More specifically, t-COD of the feedstock (influent
281 of the reactor) was 48.9 ± 3.5 g/L and s-COD 30.2 ± 5.0 g/L, while the values of the
282 same parameters in the effluent were 46.3 ± 6.2 g/L and 27.6 ± 4.0 g/L respectively. The
283 percentage of t-COD decrease reached 5.3%, which indicates that at the operating
284 HRT there was no significant methanogenic activity that could cause further COD
285 reduction. At the same time, s-COD is stable, with a minimum decrease after 100 d,
286 indicating that soluble substances have been converted to VFAs, H_2 and CO_2 . It seems
287 that hydrolysis of solids has not taken place as the s-COD has not increased and it is
288 also confirmed from **Fig. 2**, where no substantial TSS decrease is observed. This was
289 expected since the solid substances included in the feedstock are cellulose,
290 hemicellulose and lignin from the DN fluffy pulp and the cell wall of fruit and
291 vegetables which are rather difficult to hydrolyze at such low HRT.

292

293

294 **Figure 3.** Evolution of total (t-COD) and soluble COD (s-COD) concentration in the
 295 influent and effluent during acidogenesis for each HRT and pH tested.

296

297 Regarding the evolution of carbohydrates, 77% of the influent **t-Carbohydrates**
 298 was converted to VFAs, EtOH and hydrogen production. For the HRT of 2 d, the
 299 consumption ranged between 79.2% and 79.8% depending on the pH, while at the
 300 HRT of 1.5 d the reduction of **t-Carbohydrates** was 74.9%. As presented in **Fig. 4**, the
 301 **s-Carbohydrates** were almost totally consumed and reached 96.9% reduction.
 302 Hydrolysis is of great importance in anaerobic digestion processes since it is often
 303 considered as the rate-limiting step in biogas production (Graunke and Wilkie, 2014).

304

305 **Figure 4.** Evolution of total (**t-Carbohydrates, t-CH**) and soluble carbohydrates (**s-**
 306 **Carbohydrates, s-CH**) concentration in the influent and effluent during acidogenesis
 307 for each HRT and pH tested.

308

309 VFAs and EtOH concentrations seem to fluctuate during the acidogenesis stage
 310 (**Fig. 5**). This is probably attributed to the complexity of the feedstock as well as to
 311 potential differences in the microbial population that were added with each feeding. In
 312 more detail, at HRT 2 d and pH 5.5 (Run I), acetic acid reached 6 g/L while propionic
 313 acid presented a concentration of 4 g/L in the beginning but further on it stabilized
 314 below 1 g/L. Butyric acid concentration ranged between 0 to 6.6 g/L and caproic acid
 315 presented a maximum of 4 g/L. EtOH concentration showed an increasing trend when
 316 total VFAs were decreasing, reaching a maximum of 9.7 g/L. Mean value of the total
 317 main end-products of this Run was 12 ± 3.5 g/L with 6.1 ± 1.8 g/L total VFAs.

318 The second Run, which corresponds to operating conditions of HRT 2 d and
 319 pH 6.0, presents a more stable operation. The concentrations of products that are of

320 high interest for hydrogen production, i.e acetic and butyric acid, and ethanol were
321 3.2 ± 0.75 g/L, 3.9 ± 1.9 g/L and 4.5 ± 2.1 g/L respectively, while propionic acid which
322 has an inverse correlation with gas production was 0.5 ± 0.25 g/L. It should be noted
323 that pathways that enhance H₂ production are linked with acetic and butyric acid
324 formation, while ethanol is a by-product of an H₂-neutral pathway (De Gioannis et al.,
325 2017). It's worth mentioning that caproic acid during Run II reached 6.1 ± 0.9 g/L at
326 day 100 causing an increase of the total main end products' concentration at 15.8 ± 2.2
327 g/L. Mean total VFAs concentration of this Run was almost double than the previous,
328 reaching 11.7 ± 3.4 g/L.

329 On the third run, there has been an attempt to reduce HRT at 1.5 d, since it is
330 widely reported that enhanced hydrogen production could be achieved when HRTs are
331 shortened (Dareioti and Kornaros, 2014; Scoma et al., 2013). In addition, a reduction
332 of pH value was imposed from 6.0 to 5.5 to avoid inhibition of the following
333 methanogenic step due to increased concentration of Na⁺ and/or K⁺ (used for pH
334 control). Regarding VFAs production, results ranged at the same levels as in the
335 previous Run. Mean total VFAs concentration was 10.6 ± 1.4 g/L, with acetic acid,
336 propionic acid, butyric acid, and EtOH being 3.1 ± 1 g/L, 0.66 ± 0.14 g/L, 2.6 ± 0.7 g/L
337 and 5.4 ± 1.0 g/L respectively. Caproic acid was also high (3.6 ± 0.4 g/L) and total main
338 end products were 15.4 ± 1.6 g/L. This Run showed better results on the production of
339 VFAs and ethanol, compared with the first one that had the same pH (5.5) and
340 increased HRT (2 d). This is probably attributed to the adaptation of microorganisms
341 to the fermentable substrate.

342

343

344 **Figure 5.** Evolution of main end-products (VFAs and EtOH) during acidogenesis for
 345 each HRT and pH tested

346

347 Besides VFAs, hydrogen production was also favoured by the pH increase
 348 from 5.5 to 6.0. H_2 production among the Runs was 0.72 ± 0.3 , 1.93 ± 0.17 and
 349 0.29 ± 0.08 L H_2 /L feed, while the percentage of H_2 in the biogas produced reached
 350 21.5%, 27.9% and 15.3 % for Run I, II and III respectively (**Fig. 6**). [Shen et al. \(2013\)](#)
 351 report a gradual decrease of H_2 biogas content, at a two-stage system for the co-
 352 digestion of fruit and vegetables waste (FVW) with food waste (FW), when OLR was
 353 increased. More specifically, H_2 percentage reached 30% during the start-up of the
 354 system with an OLR at 2 $g_{VS}/L.d$, but followed a descending rate up to 10% at an OLR
 355 10 $g_{VS}/L.d$.

356 Although it has been widely reported that hydrogen yield increases with the
 357 reduction of HRT (Dareioti and Kornaros, 2014; Scoma et al., 2013), probably due to
 358 washing out of methanogens and the differences in growth rates between hydrogen

359 producing and consuming bacteria, it seems that HRT alone cannot be considered a
 360 sufficient controlling parameter of hydrogen production. Alexandropoulou et al
 361 (2018), report maximum production rates at low HRTs, regarding H₂ formation from
 362 the treatment of food industry wastes (FIW) but mention that maximum production
 363 yields, in terms of L H₂/ kg FIW were obtained at higher HRTs (Alexandropoulou et
 364 al., 2018). The nature of feedstock and its hydrolytic needs, operational pH and
 365 temperature play also a significant role on the final production of biogas as well as on
 366 its H₂ content (Ghimire et al., 2015).
 367

368
 369 **Figure 6.** Evolution of biogas, hydrogen and hydrogen yield during acidogenesis for
 370 each HRT and pH tested.

371

372 *3.3 Methanogenic reactor.*

373

374 During methanogenesis, the bio-methane production by the methanogenic

375 reactor (2nd stage of anaerobic digestion) was monitored. The feeding substrate to the
376 methanogenic reactor was the effluent from the acidogenic one. HRT was stable at 25
377 days for the corresponding runs of acidogenesis I-IIa. Subsequently, attempts were
378 made to reduce the HRT of the methanogenic reactor in the aim to increase methane
379 productivity. Initially, a decrease was imposed to 15 days (Run IIb), followed by
380 further reduction of HRT to 10 d (Run IIc). pH monitoring was performed manually
381 and ranged from 7.1 to 8.3. Furthermore, it was considered of great importance to
382 investigate the possibility of one-stage methanogenesis, in order to assess and compare
383 the digestion performance of the two systems in terms of bio-methane production and
384 digestion stability. This is crucial for both system design and developing operating
385 guidelines for the effective valorisation of DN hydrolysate and EFP through bioenergy
386 production. To this end, the methanogenic reactor after the end of Run IIc operated as
387 one-stage by disconnecting it from the acidogenic reactor and fed directly with the
388 waste stream (Run IV).

389 Initially, the bioreactor was filled with the anaerobic sludge inoculum and
390 therefore the microbial community was washed out daily until a steady state of solids
391 was reached at values lower than 10 g/L. TSS reduction in all Runs ranged from
392 62.5% to 65.9%, while the only Run that presented a low increase of the effluent's
393 TSS is the one corresponding to the one-stage system (**Fig. 7**). For the same HRT of
394 the two configurations, the one-stage system resulted in 8.38 ± 1.56 g/L TSS of the
395 effluent, which was 8.2% higher than the corresponding value of the two-stage system.
396 The latter is attributed to the fact that the substrate is fed directly to the methanogenic
397 reactor without any pre-treatment or prior acidogenic step. As shown in **Fig. 7** for the
398 30 days of the start-up in Run I, TSS in the effluent had a concentration of 54.85 g/L,
399 and was gradually decreased until a steady was reached at which the final

400 concentration was 8.52 ± 2.3 g/L. The initial concentration corresponds to the TSS of
 401 the used sludge, that methanogenic reactor was filled with. Mean value of VSS/TSS
 402 ratio of this run is 82.1%, which indicates an adequate level of the substrate's
 403 digestion. In Run II a further decrease of TSS concentration is observed, reaching
 404 6.53 ± 0.13 , 7.69 ± 1.8 and 5.72 ± 0.42 g/L at the steady state for Run IIa, IIb, and IIc
 405 respectively. A minimum increase of the effluent's TSS concentration in the beginning
 406 of Run IIa (8-9 g/L) is attributed to the pH shift (from 5.5 to 6.0) between the runs and
 407 the increased concentrations of Na^+ and K^+ entering the methanogenic reactor, which
 408 may have caused a stress effect on the methanogens. The improvement that is
 409 observed over time indicates that this stress effect was reversible and bacterial cells
 410 were acclimated quickly to the new conditions.
 411

412
 413 **Figure 7.** Evolution of total suspended solids (TSS) and volatile suspended solids
 414 (VSS) concentration during methanogenesis for each HRT and pH tested.
 415

416 COD was also substantially reduced, while s-COD ranged at low levels, among
 417 0.43-3.9 g/L in all Runs. The best COD removal was obtained at the two-stage system
 418 for HRT 15d, where 80.4% of the substrate's organic content was consumed. It should
 419 be noted that the system did not correspond well to the further reduction of HRT to 10
 420 d since the COD removal decreased to 62.4% (**Fig. 8**). Similar results were reported by
 421 Jo et al. (2018), where COD removal decreased as OLR was gradually increased in
 422 both single and two-stage systems, operating with food waste as substrate. More
 423 specifically, for the one-stage configuration COD removal decreased from 80.4% to
 424 25% and for the two-stage configuration the percentage decreased gradually from
 425 86.3% to 70.6%. Zuo et al. (2014) report higher percentages of COD removal that
 426 reach up to 97.1 %, with the implementation of varying recirculation rates in a two-
 427 stage system, treating fruit and vegetables. Likewise, Gulhane et al. (2016) reported a
 428 maximum COD removal of 93.5 % from the treatment of vegetable market waste in a
 429 baffled reactor.

430

431

432 **Figure 8.** Evolution of total (t-COD) and soluble COD (s-COD) concentration in the
433 influent and effluent of the methanogenic reactor.

434

435 Low concentrations of VFAs were detected in all Runs since the system
436 responded well to the operational parameters. In Run I, total VFAs reached 0.5 g/L,
437 while in the subsequent Runs (IIa-IIc), in which the pH of the acidogenic reactor was
438 higher (6.0), it seems that the elevated concentrations of Na⁺ and K⁺ due to pH control
439 in the acidogenic reactor, affected methanogens and an increase of 150 mg/L was
440 detected in VFAs. Even though high EtOH concentrations were transferred to the
441 methanogenic reactor from the first step (acidogenesis) at the two-stage system, no
442 ethanol was detected in samples obtained from the methanogenic reactor. This is
443 attributed to its full conversion to acetate (Thiele and Zeikus, 1988; Rotaru et al.,
444 2014). Similar values of VFAs (lower than 0.5 g/L) and almost neutral pH (7.0-7.6)
445 were obtained by Di Maria et al. (2014) during the anaerobic digestion of a mixed
446 waste stream that consisted of fruit and vegetables (28%), potato (55%), pasta (10%),
447 bread and paper. Comparing the two systems in terms of carbohydrates' consumption,
448 the two-stage system seems to degrade them at a greater extent (95.5-96.4%), while
449 the one stage-system managed to reach a 94.2% consumption of carbohydrates (**Fig.**
450 **9**).

451

452

453 **Figure 9.** Evolution of total (t-Carbohydrates, t-CH) and soluble carbohydrates (s-
 454 Carbohydrates, s-CH) concentration during methanogenesis.

455

456 Methane content in the two-stage system configuration ranged from 63% to
 457 77%. The latter is a rather fictitious percentage due to the conversion of dissolved CO₂
 458 to Na₂CO₃ from its reaction with NaOH, which was added in the acidogenic reactor for
 459 pH control. For the one-stage system (Run IV) the CH₄ content was 55.1±2.8 %,
 460 which is lower than the value reported by Shen at al. (2013) that reached 59-60%.
 461 Micolucci et al. (2018), report lower methane percentages in both single and two-stage
 462 pilot scale configurations that treated food waste, reaching 56±2% and 62±2% CH₄
 463 respectively. Scano et al. (2014) present a mean value of CH₄ at 55% at a pilot scale
 464 one-stage anaerobic digestion of fruit and vegetables. Methane yield in Run I and IIa
 465 reached the theoretical value (0.35 L_{CH4}/g_{t-COD removed}), while in Run IIb, IIc and in the
 466 one-stage it was 0.28, 0.15 and 0.25 L_{CH4}/g_{t-COD removed} respectively.

467 **Fig. 10** presents the methane yield (L_{CH4}/L_{feed}) and the volumetric methane

468 production rate ($L_{CH_4}/L_{reactor}\cdot d$) throughout the experimentation period. Initially,
469 methane yield reached 14-16 L_{CH_4}/L_{feed} , whereas in the subsequent Runs the decrease
470 of HRT affected the yield negatively ranging from 10.92 to 9.89 L_{CH_4}/L_{feed} for the two-
471 and one-stage configuration respectively at 15d HRT. A further reduction of HRT at
472 10 d resulted to the lowest methane yield observed (7.36 L_{CH_4}/L_{feed}). Comparing the
473 two-stage system operating at HRT 15 d (Run Iib) with the one-stage system (Run
474 IV), it is evident that the overall energy production (data not shown) by the two-stage
475 system was higher by 18.4%, as stated by other researchers as well (Shen et al., 2013;
476 Nasr et al., 2012). This calculation was based on the sum of energy produced by both
477 hydrogen and methane in the two systems using the Lower Heating Values (LHV) of
478 both gases (120 MJ/kg H_2 and 50 MJ/kg CH_4), ignoring the higher energy
479 consumption of the two-stage system due to insufficiency of data available at the lab-
480 scale level. According to Schievano et al. (2014), higher energy recovery from two-
481 stage systems compared to single stage is highlighted by many authors. Percentages of
482 energy increment from 20% to 60% under thermophilic or mesophilic operations have
483 been attributed to the phase separation of two-stage configurations (Schievano et al.,
484 2014). Besides substrate conversion rates to energy, two-stage systems are considered
485 to be more stable, reliable and resilient (Castellano-Hinojosa et al., 2018).

486

487 **Figure 10.** Evolution of methane yield and volumetric methane production rate during
 488 methanogenesis.

489

490 **4. Conclusions**

491 Co-digestion of DN hydrolysate and EFP at a 60:40 (v/v) ratio was tested in a two-
 492 and one-stage anaerobic digestion configuration. Run II, which corresponds to
 493 operational conditions in the acidogenic reactor of pH 6.0 and HRT 2 d, exhibited the
 494 highest H₂ yield (3.7 L_{H2}/L_{feed}) with a mean value of 1.93±0.17 L_{H2}/L_{feed}. The highest
 495 CH₄ yield (16 L_{CH4}/L_{feed}) was achieved in the two-stage system (Run I) in which the
 496 operating conditions were pH 5.5 HRT 2 d in the acidogenic reactor and HRT 25 d in
 497 the methanogenic one, with a mean value of 14.26±1.00 L_{CH4}/L_{feed}. The system
 498 operated successfully at HRT 2 d and pH 6.0 for the acidogenic reactor and 15 d for
 499 the methanogenic reactor. In terms of total energy production, the two-stage
 500 configuration had higher performance (by 18.4%) compared to one-stage.

501

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505

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1 **USED DISPOSABLE NAPPIES AND EXPIRED FOOD**
2 **PRODUCTS VALORIZATION THROUGH ONE- & TWO-STAGE**
3 **ANAEROBIC CO-DIGESTION**

4 Konstantina Tsigkou^a, Panagiota Tsafrakidou^b, Alexandros Kopsahelis^a, Dimitris
5 Zagklis^b, Constantina Zafiri^b, Michael Kornaros^{a,*}

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7 ^a *Laboratory of Biochemical Engineering and Environmental Technology (LBEET),*
8 *Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, University Campus, Patras,*
9 *GR-26504, Greece*

10 ^b *Green Technologies Ltd, 5 Ellinos Stratiotou Str., Patras, GR-26223, Greece*

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15 *Corresponding author. Tel.: +30 2610 997418; Fax: +30 2610 969584

16 *E-mail address:* kornaros@chemeng.upatras.gr (M. Kornaros)

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24

25 **ABSTRACT**

26

27 In the present work, an innovative approach of used disposable nappies (DN)
28 treatment is presented aiming at energy recovery through anaerobic co-digestion of
29 their biodegradable content along with a waste fraction containing expired food
30 products (EFP). More specifically, a mixture of hydrolysate, prepared from used
31 disposable nappies with pulverized fruits/vegetables that have lost their retail value,
32 was used as feedstock in two- and one-stage mesophilic anaerobic digestion systems
33 at a 60:40 (v/v) ratio. For the two-stage experiments, different combinations of pH
34 and Hydraulic Retention Time (HRT) were tested in the acidogenic and
35 methanogenic reactor. The performance of the system, operated at steady-state
36 conditions, in terms of COD removal, digestion stability, and biofuels (H₂ and CH₄)
37 production, was compared with that obtained from the one-stage configuration. The
38 comparison between the two systems revealed that COD removal reached 80% in the
39 two-stage system, but only 68% in the one-stage. At HRT 25d the yield of produced
40 methane in the methanogenic reactor of the two-stage system reached the theoretical
41 value of 0.35 L_{CH₄}/g_{t-COD} removed. Comparing the two-stage system, operated at
42 HRT 15d, with the one-stage system, it was evident that the energy production of the
43 two-stage system was higher by 18.4%.

44

45 *Keywords:* disposable nappies, expired food products, anaerobic co-digestion, two-
46 stage system, biogas, biohydrogen

47

48

49 **1. Introduction**

50

51 Used disposable nappies represent 2% to 15% of the municipal solid waste
52 (MSW) globally (Arena et al., 2016; Espinosa-Valdemar et al., 2014). Among the
53 components comprising a disposable nappy are fluffy pulp (cellulose fibres), which is
54 part of the absorbent core layer, and the excreta (urine and faeces) it contains, thus
55 making organic materials a notable percentage in this type of waste reaching almost
56 90% (Colon et al., 2010). Despite the significant proportion of recyclable materials in
57 this waste stream, it is currently disposed of to landfills or led to incineration, due to
58 its collection with unsorted Municipal Solid Wastes (MSW) (Colon et al., 2013;
59 Arena et al., 2016). Used disposable nappies are characterized by a residency time in
60 landfills up to 500 years. Therefore, it is essential to investigate various sustainable
61 management solutions for the effective treatment of these wastes and promote
62 separate collection towards their valorization.

63 In addition, EU food waste from wholesale and retail account for almost 5
64 million tonnes per year (Stenmarck et al., 2016). This sector of the supply chain in
65 Greece and other EU countries follows a returning policy of the expired food products
66 (EFP) or the faulty products that do not preserve their retail value to the production
67 companies. Only fruit and vegetables are treated with conventional waste
68 management methods such as landfilling, leaving their valuable components like
69 carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals unexploited (Han et al., 2015; Nathia-Neves et
70 al., 2018).

71 The solution of landfilling should no longer play the pivotal role of waste
72 management, due to both environmental and public health safety risks but also
73 because of waste framework directives. EU Landfill Directive (99/31/EC) of 31st

74 April, necessitates the reduction of biodegradable waste disposal in landfills, while
75 European Directive 2008/98/EC (08/98/EC) suggests that the following waste
76 hierarchy should be applied: prevention, preparation for re-use, recycling, other
77 recovery (such as energy recovery) and disposal. Energy recovery can be achieved
78 through anaerobic digestion (AD), which is widely used for the treatment of MSW
79 equally with composting (Paramaguru et al., 2017). Besides energy generation, AD
80 presents other benefits as well, like greenhouse gas mitigation and a stabilized
81 digestate that could be also valorized through composting for soil enhancement
82 (Dogan and Demirer, 2012; Behera et al., 2010). The efficiency of the process
83 depends on various parameters that have been reported in literature, like one- or two-
84 stage systems (Nathao et al., 2013; Micolucci et al., 2018), pH (Dareioti et al., 2014;
85 Paramaguru et al., 2017), HRT (Dareioti and Kornaros, 2014, 2015), pretreatment
86 (Naran et al., 2016), substrate shift (Carvalheira et al., 2018), microbial community
87 and characteristics (Zhao et al., 2018) and co-digestion which is a well-established
88 technology with consistent results in boosting the production of gaseous biofuels
89 (Edwards et al., 2017). One of the advantages of the simultaneous digestion of two or
90 more substrates is that it dilutes toxic compounds that usually inhibit the operation of
91 the bioreactors (Angeriz-Campoy et al., 2015), but also facilitates the anaerobic
92 digestion process by balancing nutrients and reducing the cost of managing each
93 stream separately via equipment sharing.

94 Besides the use of two or more substrates as feedstock, one- or two-stage
95 configuration of the anaerobic system is crucial for the final energy production and
96 stability of the process (Schievano et al., 2014). The separation of the H₂ production
97 phase from methanogenesis has been investigated by many scientists. Regarding food
98 waste, Xiao et al. (2018) reported recently a comparison between one- and two-stage

99 anaerobic digestion under thermophilic conditions, where they compared energy
100 yields, methane content of the produced biogas, methane yields, and reaction rates
101 between the two configurations. Another late attempt compared the energy recovery
102 between the two configurations for the anaerobic digestion of food waste (De
103 Gioannis et al., 2017), while Voelklein et al. (2016) studied the impact of loading rate
104 increase on the two-stage anaerobic digestion compared to a single-stage system.

105 The objective of this study was to investigate the co-digestion of used
106 disposable nappies (DN) and expired food products (EFP) through one- and two-stage
107 anaerobic continuous systems, by exploiting their energy content in the most efficient
108 and productive way in terms of energy, i.e. hydrogen and methane production. The
109 obligatory pre-treatment step of DN, for the removal of plastics and other non-bio-
110 degradable polymers for the preparation of the hydrolysate that contains the
111 biodegradable material, results to a waste stream with a low COD value that comes
112 mostly from cellulose fibres and excreta. Regarding lignocellulosic materials like DN,
113 the rate limiting step of anaerobic digestion is hydrolysis, which is hindered by the
114 their complex and compact structure and the presence of lignin that inhibits enzymatic
115 activity (Yu et al., 2004; Ma et al., 2013). In order to surpass this adversity, EFP that
116 contain high amounts of soluble organic material and COD content, were introduced
117 in the feedstock of the digesters. Co-digestion was proposed as a management
118 solution, for the simultaneous valorisation of a not easily degradable waste stream
119 (DN) and the waste stream (food waste) that represents the highest percentage among
120 the Municipal Solid Wastes (Abad et al., 2019). Gaseous biofuels production was
121 monitored in order to draw comparative conclusions on the efficiency of each
122 configuration. More specifically, in the two-stage system, different combinations of
123 pH and HRT were tested, while both reactors were also operated as one-stage systems

124 for comparison reasons.

125

126 **2. Materials and Methods**

127

128 *2.1 Anaerobic digestion feedstock and inoculum*

129

130 A hydrolysate from used disposable nappies (DN), prepared according to
131 Conway et al. (1996), was used as feedstock for co-digestion with pulped fruit and
132 vegetables that have lost their retail value. Used disposable nappies were obtained
133 from a Greek private nursery in Patras (Achaia, Greece), while the expired food
134 products (EFP) containing only fruits and vegetables, originated from a Greek
135 Supermarket chain. The ratio of the feedstock was 60% DN and 40% (v/v) EFP. Both
136 EFP and DN were stored separately at -18 °C until further use.

137 Anaerobic sludge, obtained from a wastewater treatment plant in
138 Metamorphosis (Attiki, Greece), was used as inoculum at 15% v/v in the acidogenic
139 reactor. The sludge was boiled at 100 °C for 20 min, prior to experiments, in order to
140 enrich hydrogen-producing bacteria via the deactivation of methanogens and H₂
141 consumers (Wang and Wan, 2008). The methanogenic reactor was filled (100%) with
142 the untreated sludge for the start-up of the system. The total solids (TS) content of the
143 sludge was 54.85 g/L, while the VS/TS ratio was 42%.

144

145 *2.2 Experimental set-up and procedure*

146

147 The co-digestion was carried out in mesophilic (37±0.5 °C) conditions,
148 controlled via a thermocouple and maintained constant by hot water circulation, in two

149 continuous stirred tank reactors (CSTR). The working volumes were 750 mL and 4L,
 150 for the acidogenic and the methanogenic reactor respectively. Both reactors were
 151 cylindrical, double-walled and made of stainless steel (INOX316). On top of each
 152 reactor, a geared motor drive unit was installed to ensure continuous agitation.

153 pH of the acidogenic reactor was automatically controlled (HACH controller,
 154 SC200) and kept constant with the addition of 1N NaOH-KOH solution through a
 155 peristaltic pump. Two pH values were tested (5.5 and 6.0) based on preliminary tests.
 156 The feedstock was stored in a tank, placed in a refrigerator to maintain its temperature
 157 at 4 °C and was fed to the acidogenic reactor via a precise peristaltic pump, every 1.5 h
 158 (16 times per day) for 7 sec. The effluent from this reactor was used as feedstock for
 159 the methanogenic one and was fed through a second peristaltic pump at the same
 160 frequency.

161 The system operated also as one-stage acidogenic and one-stage methanogenic.
 162 In the first case, the peristaltic pump that sent the effluent from the acidogenic reactor
 163 to the methanogenic one was deactivated, whereas in the second case, the acidogenic
 164 reactor was bypassed and the feedstock from the feeding tank was sent directly to the
 165 methanogenic reactor. The operating conditions of all tested Runs of the system are
 166 presented in **Table1**.

167

168 **Table 1.** Operating conditions of the compared anaerobic systems

Run	I	Ila	Ilb	Ilc	III	IV
One- stage	-	-	-	-	+	+
Two-stage	+	+	+	+	-	-
pH Ac.	5.5	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.5	-
HRT Ac. (d)	2	2	2	2	1.5	-

HRT Meth. (d)	25	25	15	10	-	15
Operation (d)	68	16	31	6	10	41
OLR Meth.	0.92 kg _{VS} /m ³ d (1.75 kg _{COD} /m ³ d)	0.92 kg _{VS} /m ³ d (1.75 kg _{COD} /m ³ d)	1.54 kg _{VS} /m ³ d (3.36 kg _{COD} /m ³ d)	2.3 kg _{VS} /m ³ d (4.60 kg _{COD} /m ³ d)	-	1.54 kg _{VS} /m ³ d (3.36 kg _{COD} /m ³ d)

169

170 Biogas volume was measured automatically by a custom-made device,
 171 operating via a combination of a U-tube filled with engine oil, an electron – valve and
 172 a counter. The measurement was based on counting the number of displacements of
 173 constant oil volume by the produced biogas. **Fig. 1** illustrates the experimental
 174 apparatus.

175

176 **Figure 1.** Experimental apparatus of the anaerobic co-digestion system.

177

178 2.3 Analytical methods

179

180 The characterization of each feedstock and their mixture, as well as the
 181 effluent of the reactor, included determination of the following parameters: pH,

182 alkalinity, total and soluble chemical oxygen demand (t-COD, s-COD), total and
183 soluble carbohydrates (t-Carbohydrates, s-Carbohydrates), soluble phenolic
184 compounds, total and soluble phosphorus, total (TS) and volatile (VS) solids,
185 total (TSS) and volatile (VSS) suspended solids, total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN),
186 ammonium nitrogen (NH₃-N) and fats/oils. All analyses were performed in
187 triplicate. The off-line pH was measured using a pH meter with an electrode
188 (Thermo Scientific, Orion ROSS Ultra Refillable pH/ATC Triode). Alkalinity,
189 TS, VS, TSS, VSS, COD, TKN, ammonium nitrogen, total and dissolved
190 phosphorus were determined according to *Standard Methods* (APHA, 2012).
191 Carbohydrates were measured according to Joseffson (1983), phenolic
192 compounds were determined, as syringic acid equivalents, according to
193 Waterman and Mole (1994), and fats/oils were measured after extraction with
194 hexane using a Soxhlet extractor (Velp Scientifica, SER 148).

195 Quantification of main elements C, O, H, N and S was performed on
196 freeze-dried (Telstar, LyoQuest) samples with an elemental analyser (EA3000,
197 Eurovector). Approximately 10 mg of each sample were weighed into tin
198 capsules. Samples were placed into the combustion chamber (~1000 °C) through
199 a sampling probe, then oxygen was introduced, and the temperature was raised
200 up to 1300-1400 °C, with tin acting as a catalyst. The solid samples were
201 oxidized to gases CO₂, H₂O, NO_x and SO₃ and then, after their reduction, a gas
202 mixture consisting of N₂, CO₂, H₂O and SO₂ was obtained. Finally, the gas
203 mixture was analysed through gas chromatography with a packed column
204 (Porapak Q) and a thermal conductivity detector (TCD).

205 Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) and ethanol (EtOH) were analysed by a gas
206 chromatograph (Agilent Technologies, 7890A) equipped with a capillary column

207 (DB–FFAP, 30 m in length, 0.25 mm I.D. and 0.25 μm film) and a flame
208 ionization detector. Helium was used as carrier gas.

209 Biogas samples were taken with a syringe from the top of the reactor.
210 The gas composition (H_2 , CH_4 , CO_2) was determined using a gas
211 chromatography using a capillary column (HP-PLOT/Q, 30 m in length, 0.53
212 mm I.D. and 40 μm packing film), a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and
213 nitrogen as carrier gas.

214

215 **3. Results and Discussion**

216

217 *3.1 Feedstock physicochemical characterization*

218

219 The feedstock was monitored regarding its physicochemical
220 characteristics throughout the experimentation period in order to ensure that its
221 composition remained constant. As shown in **Table 2**, EFP present high organic
222 content and carbohydrates. More specifically, 77.7% of the carbohydrates are
223 soluble, therefore this substrate does not require further hydrolytic pre-treatment
224 prior to the anaerobic digestion process. Its pH is acidic (4.34 ± 0.22) and the
225 VS/TS ratio is 92.9%. TKN reaches 1.29 g/L and $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ 0.04 g/L, leading to the
226 conclusion that most of its nitrogen content is organic. EFP present a COD:N:P
227 ratio of 389:4:1, and a percentage of C and N of 50.6% and 2% in dry matter,
228 respectively.

229 DN hydrolysate presents lower values on almost all parameters, except
230 pH (7.77 ± 0.04) and humidity ($99.19\pm 0.10\%$). Neutral to alkaline pH value is due
231 to decomposition of urea and urate, which are present in the urine content of the

232 DN (Kirchmann and Pettersson, 1994). All nitrogen content originates from
233 ammonia (0.26 ± 0.02 g/L). Low concentrations of COD (5.87 ± 1.26 g/L),
234 carbohydrates (1.37 ± 0.13 g/L) and other characteristics are attributed to the high
235 dilution ratio due to the pre-treatment process. Cellulose and excreta of DN
236 represent the TS (8.07 ± 0.97 g/L) of this substrate. The COD:N:P ratio is
237 293.5:13:1, while the percentages of C and N reach 30.4% and 1.7% in dry
238 matter, respectively.

239 Finally, the mixture of DN and EFP (60% and 40%, v/v respectively)
240 which is used as feedstock for the process, has lower organic load than EFP with
241 t-COD 48.9 g/L. The VS/TS ratio is 86.9% and the COD:N:P is 264.6:2.3:1,
242 which is close to the optimum operational ratio for anaerobic processes (350:7:1)
243 (Nguyen et al., 2015). In addition, the C/N ratio (26.38) is also within the range
244 of the optimum values for anaerobic digestion (20-30) (Hallaji et al., 2019).

245

246 *3.2 Acidogenic reactor.*

247

248 The acidogenic reactor operated as two- and one-stage system. During
249 the two-stage operation, HRT remained constant at 2 d and two pH values were
250 tested, 5.5 and 6.0 (Run I and II), while there has been an attempt to reduce HRT
251 at 1.5 d with pH 5.5, at the one-stage treatment (Run III). A consequence of the
252 HRT reduction was the increment of the organic load rate (OLR) from 24.1 kg
253 COD/m³d to 33.9 kg COD/m³d (**Table 2**) and the reduction of the produced H₂.

254

255

256

257 **Table 2.** Physico-chemical composition of feedstock used in this study. Data are mean
 258 values (n=3, \pm SD)

Parameter	DN (SD)	EFP (SD)	Mix 60%DN:40%EFP (SD)
pH	7.77 (0.04)	4.34 (0.22)	5.01 (0.3)
t-Carbohydrates (g _{glucose} /L)	1.37 (0.13)	109.20 (5.66)	35.22 (7.3)
s-Carbohydrates (g _{glucose} /L)	0.24 (0.01)	84.90 (4.76)	23.59 (2.75)
s-phenolic compounds (g _{syringic acid} /L)	0.04 (0.00)	0.6 (0.03)	0.22 (0.05)
t-COD (g/L)	5.87 (1.26)	124.55 (2.89)	48.9 (3.5)
s-COD (g/L)	1.51 (0.22)	62.75 (1.33)	30.2 (5.0)
t-Phosphorus (g/L)	0.02 (0.00)	0.32 (0.01)	0.19 (0.02)
d-Phosphorus (g/L)	0.02 (0.00)	0.23 (0.01)	0.12 (0.01)
TKN (g/L)	0.26 (0.02)	1.29 (0.09)	0.43 (0.02)
NH ₃ -N (g/L)	0.26 (0.02)	0.04 (0.00)	0.16 (0.03)
TSS (g/L)	4.45 (0.18)	32.50 (4.44)	13.61 (2.15)
VSS (g/L)	4.30 (0.32)	30.33 (3.01)	13.17 (2.00)
TS (g/L)	8.07 (0.97)	92.51 (1.96)	26.7 (1.9)
VS (g/L)	4.99 (0.98)	85.92 (1.17)	23.2 (2.01)
Humidity (%)	99.19 (0.10)	90.75 (0.20)	97.33 (0.40)
C (%) *	30.4	50.6	47.5
N (%) *	1.7	2	1.8
H (%) *	5	2.5	3.2
O (%) *	43.7	33.5	36.1
S (%) *	0.2	0.2	0.2
C/N	17.88	25.30	26.38

259 *% in dry matter

260 In addition, TSS and VSS presented in **Fig. 2**, remained at a range between 10
 261 to 15 g/L throughout the operation of acidogenesis. Therefore, in order to ensure that
 262 sufficient hydrolysis of the organic matter took place, the HRT was kept at 2 d even
 263 though in literature it has been reported that this stage can last hours (Dareioti et al.,
 264 2014; Lee et al., 2013). TSS of the acidogenic reactor effluent were 12.69 ± 1.83 g/L
 265 with 95.5% of them being VSS. De Gioannis et al. (2017), mention a VS removal of
 266 the same magnitude during acidogenesis of food waste with HRT 26 h and conclude
 267 that CO₂ production is responsible for the limited loss of organic carbon (De Gioannis
 268 et al. 2017). They report that most of the carbon content remains in the liquid phase of
 269 the acidogenesis effluent and can be further converted to methane during
 270 methanogenesis in the second reactor, as previously reported by other researchers
 271 (Alibardi and Cossu, 2016). On the contrary, Ganesh et al. (2014) report high
 272 solubilization of the fruit and vegetable waste they treated, during a two-stage
 273 operation at an OLR of 7.0 Kg_{VS}/m³d with a pH value of 5.5-6.2.

274

275

276 **Figure 2.** Evolution of total suspended solids (TSS) and volatile suspended solids
277 (VSS) concentration during acidogenesis for each HRT and pH tested.

278

279 The extent of hydrolysis taking place during acidogenesis was also monitored
280 by the evolution of COD (**Fig. 3**). More specifically, t-COD of the feedstock (influent
281 of the reactor) was 48.9 ± 3.5 g/L and s-COD 30.2 ± 5.0 g/L, while the values of the
282 same parameters in the effluent were 46.3 ± 6.2 g/L and 27.6 ± 4.0 g/L respectively. The
283 percentage of t-COD decrease reached 5.3%, which indicates that at the operating
284 HRT there was no significant methanogenic activity that could cause further COD
285 reduction. At the same time, s-COD is stable, with a minimum decrease after 100 d,
286 indicating that soluble substances have been converted to VFAs, H_2 and CO_2 . It seems
287 that hydrolysis of solids has not taken place as the s-COD has not increased and it is
288 also confirmed from **Fig. 2**, where no substantial TSS decrease is observed. This was
289 expected since the solid substances included in the feedstock are cellulose,
290 hemicellulose and lignin from the DN fluffy pulp and the cell wall of fruit and
291 vegetables which are rather difficult to hydrolyze at such low HRT.

292

293

294 **Figure 3.** Evolution of total (t-COD) and soluble COD (s-COD) concentration in the
 295 influent and effluent during acidogenesis for each HRT and pH tested.

296

297 Regarding the evolution of carbohydrates, 77% of the influent t-Carbohydrates
 298 was converted to VFAs, EtOH and hydrogen production. For the HRT of 2 d, the
 299 consumption ranged between 79.2% and 79.8% depending on the pH, while at the
 300 HRT of 1.5 d the reduction of t-Carbohydrates was 74.9%. As presented in **Fig. 4**, the
 301 s-Carbohydrates were almost totally consumed and reached 96.9% reduction.
 302 Hydrolysis is of great importance in anaerobic digestion processes since it is often
 303 considered as the rate-limiting step in biogas production (Graunke and Wilkie, 2014).

304

305 **Figure 4.** Evolution of total (t-Carbohydrates, t-CH) and soluble carbohydrates (s-
 306 Carbohydrates, s-CH) concentration in the influent and effluent during acidogenesis
 307 for each HRT and pH tested.

308

309 VFAs and EtOH concentrations seem to fluctuate during the acidogenesis stage
 310 (**Fig. 5**). This is probably attributed to the complexity of the feedstock as well as to
 311 potential differences in the microbial population that were added with each feeding. In
 312 more detail, at HRT 2 d and pH 5.5 (Run I), acetic acid reached 6 g/L while propionic
 313 acid presented a concentration of 4 g/L in the beginning but further on it stabilized
 314 below 1 g/L. Butyric acid concentration ranged between 0 to 6.6 g/L and caproic acid
 315 presented a maximum of 4 g/L. EtOH concentration showed an increasing trend when
 316 total VFAs were decreasing, reaching a maximum of 9.7 g/L. Mean value of the total
 317 main end-products of this Run was 12 ± 3.5 g/L with 6.1 ± 1.8 g/L total VFAs.

318 The second Run, which corresponds to operating conditions of HRT 2 d and
 319 pH 6.0, presents a more stable operation. The concentrations of products that are of

320 high interest for hydrogen production, i.e acetic and butyric acid, and ethanol were
321 3.2 ± 0.75 g/L, 3.9 ± 1.9 g/L and 4.5 ± 2.1 g/L respectively, while propionic acid which
322 has an inverse correlation with gas production was 0.5 ± 0.25 g/L. It should be noted
323 that pathways that enhance H₂ production are linked with acetic and butyric acid
324 formation, while ethanol is a by-product of an H₂-neutral pathway (De Gioannis et al.,
325 2017). It's worth mentioning that caproic acid during Run II reached 6.1 ± 0.9 g/L at
326 day 100 causing an increase of the total main end products' concentration at 15.8 ± 2.2
327 g/L. Mean total VFAs concentration of this Run was almost double than the previous,
328 reaching 11.7 ± 3.4 g/L.

329 On the third run, there has been an attempt to reduce HRT at 1.5 d, since it is
330 widely reported that enhanced hydrogen production could be achieved when HRTs are
331 shortened (Dareioti and Kornaros, 2014; Scoma et al., 2013). In addition, a reduction
332 of pH value was imposed from 6.0 to 5.5 to avoid inhibition of the following
333 methanogenic step due to increased concentration of Na⁺ and/or K⁺ (used for pH
334 control). Regarding VFAs production, results ranged at the same levels as in the
335 previous Run. Mean total VFAs concentration was 10.6 ± 1.4 g/L, with acetic acid,
336 propionic acid, butyric acid, and EtOH being 3.1 ± 1 g/L, 0.66 ± 0.14 g/L, 2.6 ± 0.7 g/L
337 and 5.4 ± 1.0 g/L respectively. Caproic acid was also high (3.6 ± 0.4 g/L) and total main
338 end products were 15.4 ± 1.6 g/L. This Run showed better results on the production of
339 VFAs and ethanol, compared with the first one that had the same pH (5.5) and
340 increased HRT (2 d). This is probably attributed to the adaptation of microorganisms
341 to the fermentable substrate.

342

343

344 **Figure 5.** Evolution of main end-products (VFAs and EtOH) during acidogenesis for
 345 each HRT and pH tested

346

347 Besides VFAs, hydrogen production was also favoured by the pH increase
 348 from 5.5 to 6.0. H_2 production among the Runs was 0.72 ± 0.3 , 1.93 ± 0.17 and
 349 0.29 ± 0.08 L H_2 /L feed, while the percentage of H_2 in the biogas produced reached
 350 21.5%, 27.9% and 15.3 % for Run I, II and III respectively (**Fig. 6**). Shen et al. (2013)
 351 report a gradual decrease of H_2 biogas content, at a two-stage system for the co-
 352 digestion of fruit and vegetables waste (FVW) with food waste (FW), when OLR was
 353 increased. More specifically, H_2 percentage reached 30% during the start-up of the
 354 system with an OLR at 2 $g_{VS}/L.d$, but followed a descending rate up to 10% at an OLR
 355 10 $g_{VS}/L.d$.

356 Although it has been widely reported that hydrogen yield increases with the
 357 reduction of HRT (Dareioti and Kornaros, 2014; Scoma et al., 2013), probably due to
 358 washing out of methanogens and the differences in growth rates between hydrogen

359 producing and consuming bacteria, it seems that HRT alone cannot be considered a
 360 sufficient controlling parameter of hydrogen production. Alexandropoulou et al
 361 (2018), report maximum production rates at low HRTs, regarding H₂ formation from
 362 the treatment of food industry wastes (FIW) but mention that maximum production
 363 yields, in terms of L H₂/ kg FIW were obtained at higher HRTs (Alexandropoulou et
 364 al., 2018). The nature of feedstock and its hydrolytic needs, operational pH and
 365 temperature play also a significant role on the final production of biogas as well as on
 366 its H₂ content (Ghimire et al., 2015).
 367

368
 369 **Figure 6.** Evolution of biogas, hydrogen and hydrogen yield during acidogenesis for
 370 each HRT and pH tested.

371

372 *3.3 Methanogenic reactor.*

373

374 During methanogenesis, the bio-methane production by the methanogenic

375 reactor (2nd stage of anaerobic digestion) was monitored. The feeding substrate to the
376 methanogenic reactor was the effluent from the acidogenic one. HRT was stable at 25
377 days for the corresponding runs of acidogenesis I-IIa. Subsequently, attempts were
378 made to reduce the HRT of the methanogenic reactor in the aim to increase methane
379 productivity. Initially, a decrease was imposed to 15 days (Run IIb), followed by
380 further reduction of HRT to 10 d (Run IIc). pH monitoring was performed manually
381 and ranged from 7.1 to 8.3. Furthermore, it was considered of great importance to
382 investigate the possibility of one-stage methanogenesis, in order to assess and compare
383 the digestion performance of the two systems in terms of bio-methane production and
384 digestion stability. This is crucial for both system design and developing operating
385 guidelines for the effective valorisation of DN hydrolysate and EFP through bioenergy
386 production. To this end, the methanogenic reactor after the end of Run IIc operated as
387 one-stage by disconnecting it from the acidogenic reactor and fed directly with the
388 waste stream (Run IV).

389 Initially, the bioreactor was filled with the anaerobic sludge inoculum and
390 therefore the microbial community was washed out daily until a steady state of solids
391 was reached at values lower than 10 g/L. TSS reduction in all Runs ranged from
392 62.5% to 65.9%, while the only Run that presented a low increase of the effluent's
393 TSS is the one corresponding to the one-stage system (**Fig. 7**). For the same HRT of
394 the two configurations, the one-stage system resulted in 8.38 ± 1.56 g/L TSS of the
395 effluent, which was 8.2% higher than the corresponding value of the two-stage system.
396 The latter is attributed to the fact that the substrate is fed directly to the methanogenic
397 reactor without any pre-treatment or prior acidogenic step. As shown in **Fig. 7** for the
398 30 days of the start-up in Run I, TSS in the effluent had a concentration of 54.85 g/L,
399 and was gradually decreased until a steady was reached at which the final

400 concentration was 8.52 ± 2.3 g/L. The initial concentration corresponds to the TSS of
 401 the used sludge, that methanogenic reactor was filled with. Mean value of VSS/TSS
 402 ratio of this run is 82.1%, which indicates an adequate level of the substrate's
 403 digestion. In Run II a further decrease of TSS concentration is observed, reaching
 404 6.53 ± 0.13 , 7.69 ± 1.8 and 5.72 ± 0.42 g/L at the steady state for Run IIa, IIb, and IIc
 405 respectively. A minimum increase of the effluent's TSS concentration in the beginning
 406 of Run IIa (8-9 g/L) is attributed to the pH shift (from 5.5 to 6.0) between the runs and
 407 the increased concentrations of Na^+ and K^+ entering the methanogenic reactor, which
 408 may have caused a stress effect on the methanogens. The improvement that is
 409 observed over time indicates that this stress effect was reversible and bacterial cells
 410 were acclimated quickly to the new conditions.
 411

412
 413 **Figure 7.** Evolution of total suspended solids (TSS) and volatile suspended solids
 414 (VSS) concentration during methanogenesis for each HRT and pH tested.
 415

416 COD was also substantially reduced, while s-COD ranged at low levels, among
 417 0.43-3.9 g/L in all Runs. The best COD removal was obtained at the two-stage system
 418 for HRT 15d, where 80.4% of the substrate's organic content was consumed. It should
 419 be noted that the system did not correspond well to the further reduction of HRT to 10
 420 d since the COD removal decreased to 62.4% (**Fig. 8**). Similar results were reported by
 421 Jo et al. (2018), where COD removal decreased as OLR was gradually increased in
 422 both single and two-stage systems, operating with food waste as substrate. More
 423 specifically, for the one-stage configuration COD removal decreased from 80.4% to
 424 25% and for the two-stage configuration the percentage decreased gradually from
 425 86.3% to 70.6%. Zuo et al. (2014) report higher percentages of COD removal that
 426 reach up to 97.1 %, with the implementation of varying recirculation rates in a two-
 427 stage system, treating fruit and vegetables. Likewise, Gulhane et al. (2016) reported a
 428 maximum COD removal of 93.5 % from the treatment of vegetable market waste in a
 429 baffled reactor.

430

431

432 **Figure 8.** Evolution of total (t-COD) and soluble COD (s-COD) concentration in the
433 influent and effluent of the methanogenic reactor.

434

435 Low concentrations of VFAs were detected in all Runs since the system
436 responded well to the operational parameters. In Run I, total VFAs reached 0.5 g/L,
437 while in the subsequent Runs (IIa-IIc), in which the pH of the acidogenic reactor was
438 higher (6.0), it seems that the elevated concentrations of Na⁺ and K⁺ due to pH control
439 in the acidogenic reactor, affected methanogens and an increase of 150 mg/L was
440 detected in VFAs. Even though high EtOH concentrations were transferred to the
441 methanogenic reactor from the first step (acidogenesis) at the two-stage system, no
442 ethanol was detected in samples obtained from the methanogenic reactor. This is
443 attributed to its full conversion to acetate (Thiele and Zeikus, 1988; Rotaru et al.,
444 2014). Similar values of VFAs (lower than 0.5 g/L) and almost neutral pH (7.0-7.6)
445 were obtained by Di Maria et al. (2014) during the anaerobic digestion of a mixed
446 waste stream that consisted of fruit and vegetables (28%), potato (55%), pasta (10%),
447 bread and paper. Comparing the two systems in terms of carbohydrates' consumption,
448 the two-stage system seems to degrade them at a greater extent (95.5-96.4%), while
449 the one stage-system managed to reach a 94.2% consumption of carbohydrates (**Fig.**
450 **9**).

451

452

453 **Figure 9.** Evolution of total (t-Carbohydrates, t-CH) and soluble carbohydrates (s-
 454 Carbohydrates, s-CH) concentration during methanogenesis.

455

456 Methane content in the two-stage system configuration ranged from 63% to
 457 77%. The latter is a rather fictitious percentage due to the conversion of dissolved CO₂
 458 to Na₂CO₃ from its reaction with NaOH, which was added in the acidogenic reactor for
 459 pH control. For the one-stage system (Run IV) the CH₄ content was 55.1±2.8 %,
 460 which is lower than the value reported by Shen at al. (2013) that reached 59-60%.
 461 Micolucci et al. (2018), report lower methane percentages in both single and two-stage
 462 pilot scale configurations that treated food waste, reaching 56±2% and 62±2% CH₄
 463 respectively. Scano et al. (2014) present a mean value of CH₄ at 55% at a pilot scale
 464 one-stage anaerobic digestion of fruit and vegetables. Methane yield in Run I and IIa
 465 reached the theoretical value (0.35 L_{CH₄}/g_{t-COD removed}), while in Run IIb, IIc and in the
 466 one-stage it was 0.28, 0.15 and 0.25 L_{CH₄}/g_{t-COD removed} respectively.

467 **Fig. 10** presents the methane yield (L_{CH₄}/L_{feed}) and the volumetric methane

468 production rate ($L_{CH_4}/L_{reactor}\cdot d$) throughout the experimentation period. Initially,
469 methane yield reached 14-16 L_{CH_4}/L_{feed} , whereas in the subsequent Runs the decrease
470 of HRT affected the yield negatively ranging from 10.92 to 9.89 L_{CH_4}/L_{feed} for the two-
471 and one-stage configuration respectively at 15d HRT. A further reduction of HRT at
472 10 d resulted to the lowest methane yield observed (7.36 L_{CH_4}/L_{feed}). Comparing the
473 two-stage system operating at HRT 15 d (Run Iib) with the one-stage system (Run
474 IV), it is evident that the overall energy production (data not shown) by the two-stage
475 system was higher by 18.4%, as stated by other researchers as well (Shen et al., 2013;
476 Nasr et al., 2012). This calculation was based on the sum of energy produced by both
477 hydrogen and methane in the two systems using the Lower Heating Values (LHV) of
478 both gases (120 MJ/kg H_2 and 50 MJ/kg CH_4), ignoring the higher energy
479 consumption of the two-stage system due to insufficiency of data available at the lab-
480 scale level. According to Schievano et al. (2014), higher energy recovery from two-
481 stage systems compared to single stage is highlighted by many authors. Percentages of
482 energy increment from 20% to 60% under thermophilic or mesophilic operations have
483 been attributed to the phase separation of two-stage configurations (Schievano et al.,
484 2014). Besides substrate conversion rates to energy, two-stage systems are considered
485 to be more stable, reliable and resilient (Castellano-Hinojosa et al., 2018).

486

487 **Figure 10.** Evolution of methane yield and volumetric methane production rate during
 488 methanogenesis.

489

490 **4. Conclusions**

491 Co-digestion of DN hydrolysate and EFP at a 60:40 (v/v) ratio was tested in a two-
 492 and one-stage anaerobic digestion configuration. Run II, which corresponds to
 493 operational conditions in the acidogenic reactor of pH 6.0 and HRT 2 d, exhibited the
 494 highest H₂ yield (3.7 L_{H2}/L_{feed}) with a mean value of 1.93±0.17 L_{H2}/L_{feed}. The highest
 495 CH₄ yield (16 L_{CH4}/L_{feed}) was achieved in the two-stage system (Run I) in which the
 496 operating conditions were pH 5.5 HRT 2 d in the acidogenic reactor and HRT 25 d in
 497 the methanogenic one, with a mean value of 14.26±1.00 L_{CH4}/L_{feed}. The system
 498 operated successfully at HRT 2 d and pH 6.0 for the acidogenic reactor and 15 d for
 499 the methanogenic reactor. In terms of total energy production, the two-stage
 500 configuration had higher performance (by 18.4%) compared to one-stage.

501

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505

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